

Screening for resistance to tungro (RTV)

V. Narasimhan, V. Mariappan, S. Muthusamy, and S. Rajasekaran, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, India

We evaluated 35 promising rice cultures for RTV resistance in the field. The trials were laid out in the 1983 dry season and the 1984 wet and dry seasons at Madurai and Cumbum Valley, where RTV incidence was high.

Test entries were sown in two 4-m rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing, surrounded by susceptible TNI on 4 sides. The field received 100-50-50 kg NPK/ ha. RTV incidence was recorded 60 d after planting.

TNAU831520 and TNAU831521 were free of RTV; IET7492, IET7955, and ACM9 scored 2 (see table).

Seedlings of these 5 cultures and of IR50 (resistant check) and TNI (susceptible check) were artificially inoculated with RTV at 10 d after seeding, using viruliferous green

Reaction of promising rice cultures or varieties to RTV. Tamil Nadu, India.

Culture or variety	Parentage	RTV infection grade	Culture or variety	Parentage	RTV infection grade
ACM1	CO 13/IR26	5	TNAU831170	CO 41/IR50	4
ACM2	Kannagi/IR28	6	TNAU831175	CO 41/IR50	4
ACM3	BhavanilCO 36	5	TNAU831218	IR50/CHO 1039	5
ACM4	Bhavani/BC11-6-3	4	TNAU831358	CO 37/Pankhari 203	6
AMC5 (MDU2)	CO 25/IR8	5	TNAU831370	TNAU13613/	6
ACM6	IR22/CO 30	4		Pankhari 203	
ACM7	Jaya/CO 18	4	TNAU831407	IET6262/Vaigai	4
ACM8	IR8/W1263	4		(CO 37)	
ACM9	IR2153-14-1-6-2/ IR28//IR2070-625-1	2	TNAU831418	IET6262/TNAU1756	7
ACM10	IR19746-28-2-2*	5	IET6262	Pankaj/Vijaya	5
TNAU831520	PY2/IR26	0	IET7153	T141/T141 mutant	5
TNAU831521	PY2/IR36	0	IET7327	Vijaya/CR94-1512-6	6
TNAU831125	TNAU94266/IR50	3	IET7328	Vijaya/CR94-1512-6	5
TNAU831126	TNAU94266/IR50	4	IET7492	CNM539	2
TNAU831134	TNAU94266/IR50	3	IET7563	Rasi/ADT21	3
TNAU831139	TNAU20060 ² /IR50	4	IET7955	RP1883-19-2-2-1	2
TNAU831145	TNAU20060 ² /IR50	3	IR20	IR262/TKM6	5
TNAU831146	TNAU20060 ² /IR50	4	Ponni	TG65/ME80	4
TNAU831154	CO 41/IR50	6	ADT31	IRS/Cul. 340	6
TNAU831167	CO 41/IR50	4	Vaigai (CO 37)	TNI/CO 29	5
TNAU831168	CO 41/IR50	5	TNI	DGWG/Tsai-Yuan-chai	7

leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* at 2 insects/ seedling, 25 seedlings/variety. After 48 h feeding, seedlings were transplanted to pots. RTV incidence was recorded 25 d after inoculation.

TNAU831520, TNAU831521, IET7492, IET9755, and IR50 were free from infection; ACM9 scored 4 and TNI, 9. □

Breakdown of varietal resistance to bacterial blight (BB) at Pantnagar, India

M. P. Pandey, H. Singh, R.A. Singh, S.C. Mani, B. Das, and J. P. Singh, Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* has become endemic in the plains and foothills of the Himalayas in northwestern Uttar Pradesh. Genetic resistance among popular varieties of the region has been a reliable control. But resistance conferred by the traditional *Xa 4* gene has broken down. Most high yielding varieties developed so far with this gene now are susceptible to BB in the foothills. The stable donors used have been DV85 (*xa 5* × *Xa 7*), BJ1 and IET4141 (*xa 5*), and UPRB30 and UPRB31 (genes not identified).

Reaction of *O. sativa* varieties and a strain of wild species *O. barthii* to BB at Pantnagar, 1982-86.

Variety	Gene for resistance	BB reaction (0-9) ^a				
		1982	1983	1984	1985	1986
<i>Oryza sativa</i>						
TKM 6	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	3	9	7	7
Govind	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	5	9	7	7
Prasad	<i>Xa 4</i>	5	5	9	7	7
IR20	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	5	9	7	7
IR22	<i>Xa 4</i>	5	7	7	7	7
BJ 1	<i>xa 5</i>	3	3	3	3	7
IET4141	<i>xa 5</i>	3	3	3	5	7
DV 85	<i>xa 5</i> + <i>Xa 7</i>	3	3	3	1	7
Pant Dhan 4	Not known	5	5	9	7	7
UPRB 30	Not known	3	3	3	3	7
UPRB 31	Not known	3	3	3	3	7
TN1	No gene	9	9	9	9	9
<i>Oryza barthii</i>	Not known	—	—	—	0	0

^a Scored by SES.

However, these donors became very susceptible to the local BB isolate during wet season 1986, which indicates the possibility of a breakdown of the *xa 5* gene.

We clip-inoculated 43 rice varieties

at maximum tillering and scored reaction, by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, to a local isolate of BB.

It appears that the BB situation at Pantnagar (29 °N latitude, 79° 30' E